

The influence of radiographic marker registration versus a markerless trace registration method on the implant placement accuracy achieved by dynamic computer-assisted implant surgery. An in-vitro study

Short running title: Radiographic marker vs. markerless registration

Authors: Adrià Jorba-García^a, Jose Javier Bara-Casaus^b, Octavi Camps-Font^c, Rui Figueiredo^d, Eduard Valmaseda-Castellón^e

Affiliations:

^a DDS, MS. Master of Oral Surgery and Implantology, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, University of Barcelona, Barcelona (Spain).

^b MD, DDS, EBOMS, PhD. Director of the Dental and Maxillofacial Institute at the Hospital Universitari Sagrat Cor, Grupo Quirosalud. Barcelona (Spain). Head of the department of oral and maxillofacial surgery, University Hospital of Mutua Terrassa, University of Barcelona, Terrassa (Spain).

^c DDS, MS, PhD. Associate Professor of Oral Surgery, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, University of Barcelona (Spain). Researcher at the IDIBELL Institute, Barcelona (Spain).

^d DDS, MS, PhD. Professor of Oral Surgery, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, University of Barcelona (Spain). Researcher at the IDIBELL Institute, Barcelona (Spain).

^e DDS, MS, PhD. Chairman of Oral Surgery, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, University of Barcelona (Spain). Researcher at the IDIBELL Institute, Barcelona (Spain).

Correspondence:

Prof. Dr. Rui Figueiredo

Facultat de Medicina i Ciències de la Salut, Campus de Bellvitge

Universitat de Barcelona (UB)

Pavelló de Govern; 2a planta, Despatx 2.9

C/ Feixa Llarga s/n, E-08907 L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, Spain

Email: ruibarbosa@ub.edu; Tlf: + 34 93 402 42 74

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVES: This study aimed to compare the effect the radiographic marker registration (RMR) and markerless tracing registration (MTR) on implant placement accuracy using a dynamic computer-assisted implant surgery system (dCAIS). Additionally, this study aimed to assess the surgical time and whether the implant location influences the accuracy of the two registration methods.

METHODS: 136 dental implants were randomly allocated to the RMR or MTR group and were placed with a dCAIS in resin models. Preoperative and postoperative Cone Beam Computer Tomograms (CBCT) were overlaid and implant placement accuracy was assessed. Descriptive and multivariate analysis of the data was performed.

RESULTS: Significant differences ($P < 0.001$) were found for all accuracy variables except angular deviation (RMR: 4.30° (SD: 4.37°); MTR: 3.89° (SD: 3.32°)). The RMR had a mean 3D platform deviation of 1.53 mm (SD: 0.98mm) and mean apex 3D deviation of 1.63mm (SD: 1.05mm) while the MTR had lower values (0.83mm (SD: 0.67mm) and 1.07mm (SD: 0.86mm), respectively). In the MTR group, implant placement in the anterior mandible was more accurate ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, MTR did not significantly increase the surgical time compared with RMR ($P = 0.489$).

CONCLUSIONS: MTR seems to increase the accuracy of implant placement using dCAIS in comparison with the RMR method, without increasing the surgical time. The operated area seems to be relevant and might influence the implant deviations.

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE: Considering the limitations of this *in-vitro* study, MTR seems to provide a higher accuracy in implant placement using dCAIS without increasing the surgical time. Furthermore, this method does not require radiographic markers and allows re-registration during surgery.

INTRODUCTION

Dynamic computer-assisted implant surgery (dCAIS) or navigation systems are used to provide clinicians with a real-time guidance during implant placement without the need for any guide or splint. During the surgical procedure, a stereoscopic camera and different optical trackers attached to the patient and handpiece enable the software to provide real-time feedback on the relative position of the bur or implant and the patient's anatomy in the Cone-beam Computer Tomography (CBCT) images [1–3].

These systems work with an “image-to-patient registration” which consists of virtually overlaying the 3D images of the planned implant position on those of the real patient's anatomy. This step – also known as the registration process – is critical since any inaccuracy will lead to deviations between the planned and final position of the dental implant. Currently, two registration methods have been described in dCAIS: radiographic marker-registration and markerless tracing registration [4]. The first of these methods consists of attaching a radiographic marker to the patient, usually by means of an intraoral splint or clip, which will be used during CBCT data acquisition and will be automatically recognized by the dCAIS software. This device will be placed in the same position during the surgical procedure and, together with the patient's optical tracker, will allow the software to identify the relative position of the patient's anatomy on the CBCT images [5]. The second method, markerless tracing registration, works by selecting different fiducial points on the CBCT scan images (usually on the cusps and edges of the remaining teeth) and then tracing them on the patient's anatomy using a specific probe with optical trackers, which allows the navigation system to recognize the patient's position in relation to the CBCT images [6,7].

Since two registration methods are available and no data to evaluate their impact on dental implant deviations have been published, it is of paramount importance to determine which method is more accurate. Thus, the main aim of this *in-vitro* study was to compare the effect of the two different registration methods (radiographic marker registration and markerless tracing registration) on the accuracy of implant placement using a dCAIS system. The secondary objectives of this research were to assess whether the location (maxilla versus mandible; anterior versus posterior) influenced the accuracy results of these registration methods and to compare the surgical time required with both registration approaches.

METHODS

An *in-vitro* randomized study was performed using the Navident® dynamic CAS system (ClaroNav Technology Inc. ®, Toronto, Canada). Twenty-eight resin models that simulated different clinical situations were randomly allocated to one of the 2 study groups. In the radiographic marker-registration (RMR) group, registration was performed using a specific radiographic marker placed in a thermoplastic splint during the CBCT. In the markerless tracing registration (MTR) group, registration was performed by tracing at least 3 fiducial points on the preoperative CBCT and then on the model, using a specific probe with optical trackers. An adaptation of the CONSORT guidelines [8] was followed whenever possible throughout the study. Figure 1 shows the study flowchart.

Resin models

Four types of artificial model (BoneModels®, Castellón de la Plana, Spain) were specifically developed for this study to simulate 4 different clinical situations (Figure 2):

- Maxillary anterior partial edentulism.
- Maxillary posterior partial edentulism.
- Mandibular anterior partial edentulism.
- Mandibular posterior partial edentulism.

The resin models had artificial soft tissues simulating the oral mucosa and were placed in a preclinical learning dental simulator to reproduce a clinical setting (limited mouth opening and latex face to limit visibility and to mimic the pressure of the facial soft tissues).

Sample size calculation

The sample size was calculated with G*Power v.3.1.3 (Heinrich-Heine Universität, Düsseldorf, Germany), considering that the primary outcome variable was depth deviation (in mm). Depth deviation data were extracted from a previously published study [9]. An alpha value of 0.05 and a statistical power of 80% were established. Considering that a clinically significant difference would be a reduction of 0.5mm in depth deviation, the sample size calculation yielded a total of 15 implants for each group.

Allocation and blinding

The models were randomly allocated to each group (RMR and MTR) using a webpage random generating sequence (www.randomization.com). The allocation ratio was 1:1, and the surgeon was unaware of the group assigned during the preoperative planning.

The outcome assessment was done by a third researcher that was unaware of the group allocation. However, blinding was not possible in all cases since the splint could be observed on some occasions.

Interventions

An oral surgeon (AJ-G) with more than 5 years of clinical experience in Implant Dentistry and familiar with dCAIS performed all the interventions of the study.

Radiographic marker-registration (RMR) group

For each model, a thermoplastic splint (Navistent; ClaroNav Technology Inc. ®, Toronto, Canada) was adapted to the remaining teeth. A marker with a specific radiopaque pattern was then attached to the splint and a CBCT scan (Morita®, Veraview X800; settings: 90 kV, 5 mA, $0.25 \times 0.25 \times 0.25$ mm, voxel size, 10×10 cm FOV) was obtained. (Figure 3A)

All the DICOM data were imported into the Navident 3.0 software (ClaroNav Technology Inc. ®, Toronto, Canada). The software automatically detects the radiographic marker pattern when importing the scan (Figure 3B). Manual delimitation is not required unless inaccuracies are detected.

Prosthetically driven virtual placement of the implants was made and virtual crowns were also designed. The implant positions (FDI World Dental Federation notation) were as follows:

- Maxillary anterior partially edentulous model: 1.3, 1.1, 2.1 and 2.3.
- Maxillary posterior partially edentulous model: 1.4, 1.6, 1.7, 2.4, 2.6 and 2.7.

- Mandibular anterior partially edentulous model: 3.3, 3.1, 4.1 and 4.3.
- Mandibular posterior partially edentulous model: 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 4.4, 4.6 and 4.7.

During the surgical procedure, the radiographic marker attached to the splint was replaced by an optical tracker (Figure 3C). Then, the splint with the optical tracker was firmly positioned on the remaining teeth in the exact same position and the drill axis and bur lengths were calibrated.

The clinician used the specific drilling protocol of the implant system (Bioner TopDM; Bioner®, Barcelona, Spain). Drill tip calibration was performed for each bur. The following drilling sequence was employed:

- Dental implants Ø 3.5mm:
 - Initial drill
 - Drill Ø 1.5-2.0mm
 - Drill Ø 2.2-3.3mm
- Dental implants Ø 4mm:
 - Initial drill
 - Drill Ø 1.5-2.0mm
 - Drill Ø 2.4-2.8mm.
 - Drill Ø 3.0 – 3.8mm

The implants were also calibrated before being inserted at 15 rpm with a maximum torque of 50 N.cm. The following dental implants diameters and lengths were used:

- Anterior implants: Bioner TopDM 3.5x11.5mm.
- Posterior implants: Bioner TopDM 4x10mm.

Markerless tracing registration (MTR) group

All the models were scanned (Morita®, Veraview X800; settings: 90 kV, 5 mA, 0.25 × 0.25 × 0.25 mm, voxel size, 10 × 10 cm FOV) without any specific splint or radiographic

marker. The DICOM data were then uploaded to the Navident 3.0[®] software and the implants were planned in the same way as for the RMR group.

Before starting the surgical procedure, the optical tracker was placed on the phantom (i.e. intraoral tooth-supported optical tracker for the lower jaw, and extraoral head-supported optical tracker for the maxilla). Then, 4 fiducial points located on well-defined cusps or edges of the remaining teeth were chosen on the CBCT panoramic reconstruction. These points were selected by the clinician trying to draw the largest possible geometric form. Then, a specific probe was used to spot these fiducial points on the model and trace the surface around it until 100 points were automatically detected (Figure 3 D and E). The process had to be repeated for each fiducial point. Once the markerless registration was completed, accuracy was confirmed by touching different teeth with the optical probe and confirming their position on the CBCT images.

A schematic workflow of the interventions in each group can be consulted in Figure 4. The employed optical trackers can be seen in Figure 5.

Outcome measurements:

A second CBCT scan of each model was performed after implant placement (Morita[®], Veraview X800; settings: 90 kV, 5 mA, $0.25 \times 0.25 \times 0.25$ mm, voxel size, 10×10 cm FOV). The implant accuracy variables were assessed, using EvaluNav[®] software (ClaroNav Technology Inc. [®], Toronto, Canada), by overlaying the preoperative and postoperative CBCTs and comparing the planned position with the final position of the dental implant.

The following accuracy outcome variables were measured for each implant by a second independent investigator [7]:

- Platform 3 dimensions (3D) deviation (in mm): global deviation at the entry point of the dental implant, measured in the three spatial dimensions.
- Platform 2 dimensions (2D) deviation (in mm): horizontal deviation of the dental implant at the entry point in an occlusal view, without considering depth deviation.

- Apex 3D deviation (in mm): global deviation at the apex of the dental implant, measured in the three spatial dimensions.
- Apex depth deviation (in mm): depth or vertical deviation of the apex of the dental implant
- Angular deviation (in degrees): angular deviation between the two axes of the implants.

Additionally, the surgical time was recorded for each model. Surgical time was defined as the time elapsed between placing the stent and finish placing the dental implants in the RMR group; and from the beginning of the registration process (i.e. selection of fiducial points) until the implants were placed in the MTR group.

To test intraexaminer reliability, an assessment of 36 randomly selected measurements was repeated after 4 weeks. The intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) was 0.94 (95%CI: 0.89 to 0.97; $P < 0.001$), indicating excellent absolute agreement. Specifically, the magnitude of errors of the repeated measurements were 0.22° (95%CI: 0.16 to 0.28) and 0.33 mm (95%CI: 0.27 to 0.40) for angular and linear outcome variables, respectively.

Statistical analysis

A third blinded researcher performed the statistical analysis using Stata14 software (StataCorp, College Station, TX, USA) and SPSS version 27 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The level of significance for all statistical tests was set at 5% ($P < 0.05$), using the Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons.

The normality of scale variables (Entry 3D, Entry 2D, Apex 3D, Apex vertical, Angulation and Surgical time) was explored using the Shapiro-Wilks test and the visual analysis of normal P-P graphics and box diagrams. Descriptive analysis using the median and interquartile range (IQR) was calculated when normality was rejected. Where the distribution was compatible with normality, the mean and the standard deviation (SD) were used. Descriptive analysis for bivariable categorical variables was performed through absolute and relative frequency tables.

Multilevel linear regression models were constructed to evaluate accuracy outcomes based on the registration method, using generalized estimating equations (GEE). The

GEE method was used to account for the fact that repeated observations (several implants) were made in the same model. Registration (MTR or RMR), location (maxilla or mandible), and region (anterior or posterior), and the interaction between them, were included as predictor variables. Adjusted beta coefficients for linear regression models including 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were obtained from the Wald χ^2 statistic. Pairwise comparisons between groups were performed.

RESULTS

In total, 136 implants were placed in 28 resin models: 68 implants using radiographic marker registration (RMR group) and 68 implants employing markerless tracing registration (MTR group).

Significant differences ($P < 0.001$) between the 2 groups were found for all the accuracy variables except angular deviation (Table 1). The mean 3D platform deviation was 1.53 mm (SD: 0.98mm) for RMR group, and 0.83mm (SD: 0.67mm) for the MTR group (Mean difference (MD): 0.69 mm (95% CI: 0.41 to 0.98), $P < 0.001$). Regarding apex 3D deviations, the mean values of the RMR and MTR groups were 1.63mm (SD: 1.05mm) and 1.07mm (SD: 0.86mm), respectively (MD: 0.55mm (95% CI: 0.23 to 0.88), $P < 0.001$). The angular deviation did not yield significant differences, being the MD of 0.41° (95% CI: -0.90 to 1.73 ; $P = 0.537$), with a mean deviation of 4.30° (SD: 4.37°) for the RMR group and of 3.89° (SD: 3.32°) for the MTR group. The results for all the outcome variables are summarized in Table 1 and Figure 6.

Table 2 shows the deviations observed according to the arch (maxilla or mandible) and location (anterior or posterior). In general, the MTR group implants were placed more accurately in all areas in comparison with the RMR group. The MTR registration method seems to be specially recommendable in the anterior mandible, where significant differences were found for all the deviation variables (Table 2).

Intragroup comparisons were also performed (Table 2). Implant placement with MTR was significantly less accurate in the posterior mandible compared to the anterior mandible (platform 3D; platform 2D; apex 3D) and in the anterior maxilla compared to the anterior mandible (platform 3D; platform 2D; angular deviation) ($P < 0.001$). Deviations between maxillary and mandibular and between anterior and posterior

implants were also analyzed (Table 2). In this regard, the arch did not seem to affect the accuracy significantly for either of the groups. However, the posterior implants presented higher 3D apex deviations in the MTR group and lower apex depth deviations in the RMR group (Table 2).

The markerless tracing registration method (MTR group) did not significantly increase the overall surgical time [RMR= 14.05 min (SD=3.63); MTR=15.50 min (SD=8.28) P=0.489] (Table 3). A significantly higher surgical time was only found when placing implants in the posterior region of the mandible with the markerless tracing registration system [RMR= 15.31 min (SD=0.53); MTR=20.43 min (SD=1.58) P=0.046] (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

The radiographic marker (RMR) and markerless tracing (MTR) methods are the most common registration techniques in dCAIS systems. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first study to evaluate the impact of these registration methods on implant placement accuracy when navigation devices are used. The present outcomes indicate that markerless tracing registration seems to be preferable since more accurate results are obtained without increasing the surgery time.

Registration is a crucial step when using static or dynamic CAIS systems since an error can lead to clinically relevant discrepancies between the virtual and real implant placement. Indeed, when dCAIS is involved, incorrect registration will impede a precise overlap between the patient's jaw and the preoperative CBCT [4]. Hence, several papers have been published recently to determine which registration method for dental implant placement is most accurate [10–14]. Some in-vitro studies have compared different fiducial points such as tooth areas, miniscrews, or the use of specific devices (clips, tubes, or bite indices) with radiopaque markers. More research is needed on this topic since the results are inconsistent. While one study has shown more accurate results when using bone-anchored miniscrews as fiducial points, other authors have failed to find differences between specific regions of teeth or devices provided by manufacturers [10,12]. Nevertheless, it is important to stress that all these studies have focused only on markerless tracing registration and have not provided comparisons with the traditional radiographic marker registration process.

dCAIS usually increases the surgical time in comparison with a conventional non-guided free-hand approach since several additional steps are required [7]. In this regard, the number of drills affects the length of the procedure since each drill must be calibrated before use. On the other hand, the markerless registration (MTR) process might be time-consuming since it requires the tracing of 100 points on the surface of the chosen landmarks (3 or 4 teeth). However, the present study showed that this registration method does not significantly increase the operation time in comparison with the standard procedure (RMR).

A new navigation system offers the possibility of using the patient's scan virtually to design and print an individual tray on which to attach markers. During surgery, this tray is placed on the patient's jaw according to the planned position and the dCAIS system automatically detects its relative position, achieving successful registration. However, currently this system seems to be less accurate than the conventional radiographic marker registration protocol [14]. Nevertheless, it might be an interesting concept to develop since it avoids the use of radiographic markers and tracing devices. Wu et al. [13,15] propose a registration device with radiographic markers and infrared light emission. In that study, the radiographic marker is placed during CBCT acquisition and an optical tracker with infrared light emission is attached to the marker during the surgical procedure. The system proposed by Wu et al. [13] seems to provide slightly more accurate outcomes, as it reduced the platform and apex linear deviations in comparison with the RMR group.

Recent studies appear to support the use of pair-point tracing markerless registration in the clinical setting [6,7]. Stefanelli et al. [6] retrospectively analyzed a total of 136 implants placed using dCAIS with markerless tracing registration and reported highly accurate results. A recently published randomized clinical trial using the same registration method also obtained good clinical outcomes with a mean angular deviation of 4.02° (SD= 2.80) and a linear 3D platform deviation of 1.12mm (SD= 0.38) [7]. It is important to stress that the markerless tracing registration process offers several other important advantages. Firstly, it allows the use of any recent CBCT scan of the patient. Secondly, the surgical procedure is usually more comfortable for both patient and surgeon since there is no need to wear a splint with an optical tracker. Thirdly, the splint can present small movements that might affect the implant placement accuracy, especially when the

distance between the patient optical tracker and the surgical site is large. This might explain why higher SD values for almost all accuracy variables were observed in the posterior implants of the RMR group. Finally, this method makes it possible to perform new registration if any inaccuracy is detected during the surgical procedure. Thus, taking into consideration the accuracy results obtained in the present *in vitro* study, markerless tracing registration should be used whenever possible.

The distance between the fiducial points is an important factor. Indeed, the connection between these points should generate a large geometric form to provide a more accurate registration [16]. In this regard, the distribution of bone anchored miniscrews as fiducial points during dCAIS for zygomatic implants has recently been assessed. The authors concluded that registration was more accurate when wide geometric forms connected the screws [17]. Hence, clinicians should avoid localized or unilateral fiducial markers, and in case of large edentulous areas, clinicians should consider adding artificial markers (i.e., miniscrews or adhesive devices) [18]. Also, increasing the number of reference points seems to increase the accuracy (6,19,20). This might explain the worse results obtained in the MTR group in implants placed in the posterior mandible in comparison with implants located in the anterior mandible. The simulated bilateral posterior edentulism situation did not allow a large geometric form to be drawn since the model only included canines and incisors. Rutkunas et al. [20] reported similar findings and concluded that bilateral posterior free-end edentulism yielded the worst results. Another report concluded that the distance from the radiographic marker (i.e., U-shaped tube registration device) to the surgical site did not influence the accuracy of the procedure [21].

Another important factor to consider could be the distance between the patient optical tracker and the surgical site. In the MTR group, the dCAIS system employed a head-mounted device on the patient's forehead for upper arch surgeries, while a tooth-supported tracker attached to remaining teeth using light-curing resins is used on the mandible (Figures 5C and 5D). Thus, the distance from the dental arch to the optical tracker is greater in the maxilla, which could explain the less accurate results observed in this arch. This limitation could be reduced by using an intraoral tooth-supported optical tracker for maxillary surgeries. However, extraoral optical trackers are easier to place and less time-

consuming. More research is needed to identify which additional factors might affect the implant placement accuracy.

The use of markerless pair-point registration might be challenging in fully edentulous patients since these cases usually lack clear anatomical landmarks to be used as fiducials. Therefore, additional radiopaque markers should be placed prior to the CBCT scan and traced during the registration process [22]. In this regard, Jaemsuwan et al. [23] propose to stabilize the registration stent containing the radiopaque fiducial markers with mini-implants [23].

A recent study compared 2 registration methods in static CAIS (MTR and RMR) measuring the registration accuracy during the overlaying of an intraoral scan and a CBCT scan in the presence of radiographic artifacts. Interestingly, the authors concluded that the radiographic fiducial marker-based registration should be considered when 4 or more radiopaque restorations are present [24].

The results of the present report should be interpreted with caution, especially considering that this was an *in-vitro* experimental study and that only four scenarios were tested. Also, the accuracy of the 2 registration methods was assessed indirectly since this study focused on the effect of RMR and MTR on the implant placement accuracy, which might be affected by other variables. Another possible limitation is related to the models employed. Even though these models successfully simulated different radiographic densities, it is essential to acknowledge that certain disparities may exist when comparing them to the radiological characteristics of the human tissues. Hence, further investigation comparing different registration methods in diverse scenarios (types of edentulism, location, presence of radiological artifacts, etc.) must be conducted in a clinical setting to confirm these findings.

CONCLUSIONS

Taking into consideration the limitations of this *in-vitro* study, markerless tracing registration seems to improve the accuracy of implant placement using dCAIS systems in comparison with the radiographic marker registration method, without increasing the

surgical time. The operated area appears to be a relevant variable and might have an effect on the implant deviations.

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TABLES

Table 1. Differences between the 2 study groups (RMR and MTR) for all accuracy variables.

	RMR Mean (SD)	MTR Mean (SD)	Mean difference [95% CI]	P-value
Platform 3D (mm)	1.53 (0.98)	0.83 (0.67)	0.69 [0.41-0.98]	<0.001*
Platform 2D (mm)	1.22 (0.92)	0.72 (0.71)	0.50 [0.23-0.78]	<0.001*
Apex 3D (mm)	1.63 (1.05)	1.07 (0.86)	0.55 [0.23-0.88]	<0.001*
Apex Depth (mm)	0.79 (0.50)	0.32 (0.39)	0.47 [0.33-0.60]	<0.001*
Angle (°)	4.30 (4.37)	3.89 (3.32)	0.41 [-0.90-1.73]	0.537

SD: Standard deviation; 3D: 3 dimensions; 2D: 2 dimensions; RMR: radiographic-marker registration group; MTR: markerless tracer registration group; CI: confidence interval.

Table 2. Accuracy variables of the 2 study groups stratified by arch (maxilla and mandible) and location (anterior and posterior).

Arch and location	Platform 3D (mm)			Platform 2D (mm)			Apex 3D (mm)			Apex Depth (mm)			Angle °		
	Mean (SD)			Mean (SD)			Mean (SD)			Mean (SD)			Mean (SD)		
	RMR	MTR	P-value	RMR	MTR	P-value	RMR	MTR	P-value	RMR	MTR	P-value	RMR	MTR	P-value
Anterior maxilla	1.53 (0.44)	1.20 (0.41)	0.185	1.12 (0.78)	1.13 (0.43)	1.000	1.75 (0.56)	1.01 (0.68)	0.005*	0.93 (0.41)	0.36 (0.17)	0.000*	2.84 (1.64)	4.09 (2.66)	0.667
Posterior maxilla	1.29 (0.75)	0.69 (0.45)	0.018*	1.11 (0.61)	0.57 (0.51)	0.025*	1.71 (1.32)	1.20 (0.69)	0.887	0.59 (0.46)	0.29 (0.06)	0.037*	5.08 (5.47)	5.45 (3.26)	1.000
P-value	1.000	0.003*		1.000	0.004*		1.000	1.000		0.126	0.715		0.591	1.000	
Anterior mandible	1.43 (0.64)	0.49 (0.29)	0.000*	1.07 (0.57)	0.35 (0.29)	0.000*	1.68 (0.85)	0.60 (0.28)	0.000*	0.87 (0.25)	0.30 (0.14)	0.000*	5.10 (2.74)	1.63 (1.17)	0.000*
Posterior mandible	1.85 (1.36)	0.95 (0.15)	0.030*	1.57 (1.16)	0.82 (0.14)	0.039*	1.40 (1.00)	1.41 (0.91)	1.000	0.82 (0.66)	0.35 (0.19)	0.020*	4.11 (4.08)	4.15 (3.92)	1.000
P-value	1.000	0.000*		0.641	0.000*		1.000	0.002*		1.000	1.000		1.000	0.055	
Maxilla	1.41 (0.68)	0.93 (0.74)	0.038*	1.11 (0.69)	0.83 (0.77)	0.711	1.72 (1.03)	1.11 (0.71)	0.026*	0.75 (0.58)	0.32 (0.15)	0.000*	4.03 (4.83)	4.81 (3.36)	1.000
Mandible	1.66 (1.15)	0.73 (0.52)	0.000*	1.34 (1.08)	0.60 (0.56)	0.003*	1.53 (0.98)	1.03 (1.13)	0.310	0.85 (0.51)	0.33 (0.17)	0.000*	4.57 (3.68)	2.96 (4.07)	0.520
P value	1.000	1.000		1.00	0.951		1.000	1.000		1.000	1.000		1.000	0.245	
Anterior	1.48 (0.55)	0.84 (0.79)	0.001*	1.09 (0.68)	0.74 (0.85)	0.401	1.71 (0.72)	0.81 (0.66)	0.000*	0.90 (0.35)	0.34 (0.17)	0.000*	3.97 (3.19)	2.86 (3.21)	0.983
Posterior	1.57 (1.29)	0.82 (0.46)	0.006*	1.34 (1.08)	0.69 (0.48)	0.007*	1.55 (1.23)	1.30 (0.85)	1.000	0.70 (0.63)	0.32 (0.16)	0.002*	4.59 (4.97)	4.80 (3.94)	1.000
P value	1.000	1.000		1.000	1.000		1.000	0.040*		0.677	1.000		1.000	0.151	

SD: SD: Standard deviation; 3D: 3 dimensions; 2D: 2 dimensions; RMR: radiographic-marker registration group; MTR: markerless tracer registration group; *: P <0.05.

Table 3. Surgical time outcomes for both study groups, stratified by arch and location.

	RMR Median (IQR) (minutes)	MTR Median (IQR) (minutes)	P-value
Anterior maxilla	12.81 (1.51)	14.5 (2)	0.110
Anterior mandible	12.74 (1.64)	12 (1.1)	0.236
Posterior maxilla	21.83 (3.5)	21.75 (2.66)	0.827
Posterior mandible	15.0 (0.93)	21.28 (2.81)	0.046*
TOTAL	14.05 (3.63)	15.5 (8.28)	0.489

IQR: interquartile range. RMR: radiographic-marker registration group; MTR: markerless tracer registration group.

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1: Study flowchart.

MTR: Markerless tracing registration; RMR: Radiographic marker registration.

Figure 2: Resin models simulating different clinical situations.

Figure 3: Summary of the registration process in both groups. A. Thermoplastic stent adapted to the remaining teeth and radiographic marker fixed to the stent. B. dCAIS software automatically detecting radiographic marker on CBCT scan. C. Thermoplastic stent with the optical tracker attached to the remaining teeth. The optical tracker is placed in the stent after removing the radiographic marker. D. Pair point registration by tracing fiducial points on tooth anatomy. E. Fiducial points selected on the CBCT reconstruction in the dCAIS software.

MTR: Markerless tracing registration; RMR: Radiographic marker registration;

Figure 4: Illustration showing the workflow in both study groups.

Figure 5: Fixation of the optical trackers in both groups. A. Maxilla in the RMR group. B. Lower jaw in the RMR group. C. Maxilla in the MTR group. D. Upper jaw in the MTR group.

Figure 6: Box and scatter plots of angular and linear deviations in the RMR and MTR groups. For each box, the interior line in bold shows the mean and the edges of the box are estimates of the lower and upper 95% confidence intervals (CI).

MTR: Markerless tracing registration, RMR: Radiographic marker registration,
 °: degrees, mm: millimeters, 3D three dimensions, 2D two dimensions.

